

Cell Surface Carbohydrate mediated Processes. Chemical Model for Cell-Cell and Cell-Lectin Interaction[†]

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THE carbohydrate moieties of cell surface present either as glycoproteins or glycolipids (together termed glycoconjugates) are implicated to play roles in a variety of biochemical phenomena namely, binding of bacteria to intestinal epithelium¹, aggregation of slime mold and sponge cells², yeast mating³, sperm-egg binding⁴, and interaction between cells in immune response⁵. It can function as receptors to a variety of ligands, like glycoprotein hormones, bacterial toxins (CT and DT) during their entry into cells⁶. Their presence as a class of marker molecules in plasma membrane in blood group typing, cellular differentiation and oncogenesis make their study even more interesting with specific reference to their isolation, characterisation and biosynthesis⁷. The underlying principle in all these processes is that surface glycoconjugates present in one cell bind to a complementary carbohydrate binding protein on another, resulting in specific adhesion. Alternatively, a multivalent carbohydrate binding protein, like plant lectin can cross-link carbohydrate moiety on adjacent cells. Examples of both types are known. Although functional importance of such molecules are well documented, molecules themselves have been isolated in few cases⁸. Even the actual mechanism of the process at the molecular level is not understood, mainly because of difficulties in experimentation with intact cells. There are even problems associated with the isolation of adhesion molecules using *in vitro* cell-cell interaction.

To circumvent the problem suitable cell surface analogue has been developed. The inert plastic surface derivatised with chemically defined carbohydrate ligands has been developed in detecting and isolating specific cell adhesion molecules. This has been reviewed recently⁹. On the other hand, the liposomal system with specific carbohydrate marker has been developed to study molecular mechanism of complex carbohydrate ligand interaction at the cell surface as well as to examine its possible use in the development of organ specific delivery system. The article will briefly summarise (i) the properties of a few lectins and their specificity towards simple and complex carbohydrate at the surface and problem relating to the complexity of lectin induced agglutination reaction and (ii) the use of liposomal system towards understanding molecular mechanism of lectin mediated agglutination.

Carbohydrate specificity of lectins towards simple sugar :

The lectin-group of plant proteins present in large amount in seed extracts having a remarkable ability to agglutinate erythrocytes has been known long before the host of interesting chemical and biological properties have been discovered^{10,11}. Its property to agglutinate erythrocytes in some cases with high specificity has been used in typing human blood and in the study of chemical nature of blood group substances. A surge in lectin research came primarily because of the increased agglutinability of transformed cells by plant lectins and discovery of hepatic lectin that is responsible for the maintenance of glycoconjugate level in serum. Since then studies on biochemical properties of lectins of various origin and their application in isolation of glycoproteins of functional importance became wide-spread. This is mainly because of the carbohydrate recognising properties of lectins. Tables 1 and 2 summarises carbohydrate specificity of some well studied lectins.

It is seen from Table 1 that the affinity (K_a) of sugar binding site on lectin for appropriate monosaccharide is of the order of 10^3 - $10^4 M^{-1}$. In going from monosaccharide to disaccharide, K_a increases marginally. In both cases, the binding is non-cooperative. The measured association rate constant k_f is about 10^4 - $10^5 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ which is about a factor of 100 less than that of enzyme substrate reaction and is too small for a diffusion controlled reaction. In contrast, its binding to cell is cooperative nature and occurs with $t_{1/2}$ equal to 1 to 2 min. The calculated forward rate constant k_f is 10^5 - $10^6 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ which is higher than that found for simple sugar¹². The lectin induced agglutination of cell occurs much slowly as can be seen from Fig. 1, where the average size of lectin induced cluster is plotted against time (t) for myeloma cell line. The slower rate of agglutination is rather expected but the higher value for k_f than that of simple sugar is rather surprising.

The observed higher affinity for binding of lectin to cell surface carbohydrate by 100-1 000 fold

Abbreviations: CT=Cholera toxin, DT=diphtheria toxin, DPPC=dipalmitoyl phosphatidyl choline, WGA=wheat germ agglutinin, GD_{1a}=disialoganglioside.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF LECTIN BINDING TO CARBOHYDRATE

Lectin	Carbohydrate	k_f $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	k_d s^{-1}	K_{eq} M^{-1}
ROA	p-Nitrophenyl-β-Dgal ^a	4.5×10^5	30 ± 3	1.5×10^4
	Galactose ^b	—	—	1.2×10^3
	Lac ^c	—	—	1.5×10^4
PNA	Methyl-β-D-galactoside ^d	3.7×10^4	89.4	0.94×10^3
	Methyl-β-D-lactoside ^e	4.0×10^4	29.0	1.4×10^3
	Dgal-β(1-3)-DgalNAc ^f	—	—	2.8×10^4
	Methyl-Umb-Dgal-β(1-3)-DgalNAc ^g	7.1×10^3	0.34	2.9×10^4
WGA	Methyl-Umb-glcNAc ^h	3.0×10^6	1.8×10^3	1.7×10^4
	Methyl-Umb (glcNAc) ₂ ⁱ	1.0×10^7	2.0×10^3	5.0×10^4
	p-Nitro-α-Dmannoside ^j	5.4×10^4	6.2	8.7×10^3
COLA	Methyl-Umb-(manp) ₂ ^k	—	—	$13.9 \pm 0.5 \times 10^4$
	Methyl-Umb-β-galNAc ^k	1.1×10^4	0.36	3.0×10^4

^a Ref. 18. ^b Ref. 15. ^c Olsson *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 249, 803. ^d Neurohr *et al.*, *Biochem.*, 1981, 20, 3499. ^e Neurohr *et al.*, *Biochem.*, 1982, 21, 498. ^f Neurohr *et al.*, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1982, 123, 305. ^g Looftens *et al.*, *FEBS Lett.*, 1983, 162, 193. ^h Looftens *et al.*, *J. Biochem.*, 1983, 5, (suppl. 1), 105. ⁱ Ref. 8. ^j Lewis *et al.*, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1976, 172, 689. ^k De Boeck *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1984, 259, 7067.

TABLE 2—AFFINITY PARAMETERS FOR LECTIN BINDING TO CELLS

Lectin	Cell type	K_a M^{-1}
ROA ^a	Normal calf thymocyte	4.8×10^7
WGA ^a	Normal calf thymocyte	2.6×10^6
ConA ^b	Mouse normal thymocyte	1.3×10^6
SBA ^c	Mouse normal spleen	3.0×10^6
PNA ^d	Human erythrocyte (NT)	
	A type	1.2×10^7
	B type	2.7×10^7

^a R. Kornfeld and Seimens, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 249, 1295. ^b D. Stoboj, A. S. Rosenthal and W. E. Paul, *J. Immunol.*, 1972, 108, 1. ^c A. Novogrodsky *et al.*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1973, 70, 2515. ^d Sharon *et al.*, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1977, 180, 570.

or more specific sugar in appropriate linkage giving rise to a high affinity. Alternatively, lectin may bind simultaneously two or more receptors so that observed affinity is equal to the product of separate association constants for simple sugar as it is known to be the case in the binding of monosialoganglioside GM₁ to cholera toxin^{1,2}. The cell surface has a variety of glycolipid and glycoprotein receptors, their relative proportion as well as their chemical nature are known to change upon oncogenic transformation which in turn will control the complex pattern of interaction with lectins and hence, their agglutinability as shown in Fig. 2. Further complexity would arise due to the involvement of cytoskeletal elements. It is evident that

Fig. 1. Kinetics of conA-induced agglutination of sarcoma 180 ascites cells. $\bar{X}$ represents the average number of cells per clump and calculated from the absorbance changes at 546 nm of suspension of cells when different amounts of conA ($\mu g ml^{-1}$) added to it ($\bar{X}$ is calculated according to W. A. M. Linnemars *et al.*, *Expt. Cell Res.*, 1970, 101, 191; from the spectral data of K. M. Hwang *et al.*, *Cancer Res.*, 1974, 34, 3396).

Fig. 2. Complexity of cell surface receptor-ligand interaction. Schematic pathway of lymphoid cell surface capping. (from Ref. 11).

not only the number of lectin mediated cross linkage but also lectin induced cross linking via adhesion molecule will determine final stage of agglutination. Therefore, it is difficult to obtain basic information about the specificity of lectins towards complex carbohydrate sequence and the rate and mechanism of its binding to cell surface. On the other hand, glycoconjugate embedded liposome can be used as a chemical model for the study of mechanism of cell surface receptor mediated reaction in general. The advances that have been made from studies on model liposomal systems have been recently reviewed¹⁴. We would like to focuss our attention particularly to the kinetic complexity of the reaction between liposome bearing glycoconjugate and lectin.

can be rationalised in the following way. Lectin may have extended binding site for a chain of two

Lectin binding to liposome bearing glycoconjugate :

Earlier, it has been shown that interaction between conA and carbohydrate moiety of glycoprotein lectin RCA₁ from castor bean leads to the precipitin reaction with characteristic time constant observed for the binding of lectins to cells and the precipitin complexes dissociate slowly in the presence of sugar, specific to conA. The calculated rate constant of the formation of the 1:1 RCA₁:conA and its dissociation from the measurement of time dependent appearance and disappearance of turbidity in the presence of hapten sugar is found to be $3 \times 10^3 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ and $7 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$, respectively¹⁵. Their ratio yields a value $4.3 \times 10^7 M^{-1}$ for the interaction specificity of conA towards complex carbohydrate sequence of agglutinin, RCA₁. This value is of comparable magnitude for other conA complex carbohydrate system¹⁶. This finding prompted us to develop liposome bearing glycoconjugate particularly with glycosphingolipid gangliosides because of its implicated functions listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FUNCTION OF GLYCOSPHINGOLIPID*

1. Constitutive component of outer leaflet of lipid bilayer conferring rigidity.
2. Cell surface marker and antigens.
3. Cell-cell interaction and recognition.
 - (i) Cell contact response and contact inhibition.
 - (ii) Neuroglia interaction.
 - (iii) Retinolectal recognition.
 - (iv) Neuro-muscular recognition.
4. Differentiation marker.
 - (i) Early embryo and teratocarcinoma.
 - (ii) Crypt to villus cell differentiation.
 - (iii) Erythrocyte differentiation.
 - (iv) Myogenic differentiation.
 - (v) Neuroblastoma.
 - (vi) Lymphoid cell differentiation and mitogenesis.
5. Cell growth regulation and oncogenesis.
6. Interaction with bio-active factors, bacterial toxins, glycoprotein hormones and viruses-implication as receptor.

* S. Hakamori, *Annu. Rev. Biochem.*, 1981, 50, 733.

Glycosphingolipid forms micelles at small concentrations and its C.M.C. lies in micromolar-nanomolar range depending on the nature of the carbohydrate sequence and charge¹⁷. Thus, its carbohydrate moiety is not easily accessible to even glycosidases and lectins. The accessibility, however, increases when they are embedded in liposome as well as in mixed micellar system, *i.e.* deoxycholate-lectin. It has also been found that the addition of a divalent lectin RCA₁ to a vesicle containing GM₁ (5-20%) results in the increase of turbidity due to aggregation of vesicles as shown Fig 3. In the case of bivalent lectin, SL-SL vesicles are held together by two lectin sugar bonds. The number of cross links increases as valency increases. Since initial binding (Step 1) is likely to contribute very little to the observed turbidity as lectin is

Fig 3. Mechanism of lectin (L) induced vesicle (S) aggregation through the carbohydrate moiety of glycolipid/glycoprotein embedded into the vesicles: (S) a vesicle containing glycoconjugates, (L) a bivalent lectin, and (SL) lectin-vesicle complex.

added to the solution of vesicle bearing gangliosides, the initial rate of change of turbidity is given by equation (1).

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = k_2[SL].[S] \quad (1)$$

since $t \rightarrow 0$, $[SL] \ll [S]$.

Under steady state condition, *i.e.*

$$\frac{d[SL]}{dt} = 0, [SL] \text{ is given by the equation (2).}$$

$$[SL] = \frac{k_1[S][L]}{k_2[S] + k_{-1}} \quad (2)$$

Substituting (2) in (1), one obtains equation (3)

$$\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{t \rightarrow 0} = \frac{k_2 k_1 [S]^2 [L]}{k_2 [S] + k_{-1}} \quad (3)$$

Case 1. when $k_2[S] \ll k_{-1}$, equation (3) becomes,

$$\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{t \rightarrow 0} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} \times k_2 [S]^2 [L] \quad (4)$$

Case 2. when $k_2[S] \gg k_{-1}$,

$$\left(\frac{dA}{dt}\right)_{t \rightarrow 0} = k_1 [S][L] \quad (5)$$

When $\frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} = K_{eq}$, the equilibrium constant of binding, $[L]$ and $[S]$ represent concentrations of lectin and surface carbohydrate, respectively. Values for k_1 and k_{-1} for the binding of lectins to soluble sugar is $1.6 \times 10^4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ and $20-30 s^{-1}$ (Tables 1 and 2). The vesicle aggregation is found to occur when $[L]$ and $[S]$ are in the micromolar range, the assumption $k_2[S] \ll k_{-1}$ is more satisfactory. Under these conditions, the initial rate of the vesicle aggregation is proportional to the lectin concentration as well as to the square of the concentration of available carbohydrate on the surface of vesicle as expected for a bimolecular aggregation step. Under conditions $k_2[S] \gg k_{-1}$, though difficult to achieve experimentally, rate of precipitin reaction is first order with respect to lectin and sugar. This first order dependence on lectin can be used to determine the specificity of a

soluble sugar (hapten) from experimentally observed decrease in the initial rate of vesicle aggregation. When the hapten is present in large excess, the fraction of lectin molecule available for the reaction is given by equation (6),

$$(1 - \theta) = \frac{1}{1 + K_a[H]} \quad (6)$$

where, θ is the fraction of lectin site saturated with hapten and K_a is the affinity constant of the hapten-lectin system. Since the initial velocity is proportional to the concentration of the free lectin, it is possible to calculate K_a from the slope of the plot of v_s/v_o against $[H]$ where v_s and v_o are the initial velocity in the presence and absence of hapten¹⁸. This simple method is equally applicable to water soluble complex carbohydrate.

In view of the kinetic complexity, the apparent forward rate constant of aggregation of vesicles can be estimated from the $t_{1/2}$ value (*i.e.* time for 50% change in turbidity when lectin is added to a solution of liposome bearing glycoconjugate) assuming the rate of vesicle aggregation is given by

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = k_2 c^2 \theta (1 - \theta) \quad (7)$$

where, c is the concentration of surface carbohydrate and θ is the fraction occupied by the lectin. The apparent $t_{1/2}$ depends on c and pass through a minimum as $\theta \rightarrow 1$. This has been verified experimentally¹⁸.

The dissociation complex of the type S-L-S took place slowly in the presence of soluble hapten and follows first order rate law. The calculated first order rate constant depends on the concentration of hapten and its chemical nature as found in the case of sugar induced dissociation of RCA₁-conA complex¹⁴. Hence, k_{-2} can be estimated similarly from the time dependent change in turbidity of the precipitin complex in the presence of soluble sugar. The k_2 thus can be estimated from the relation (8),

$$k_2 = k_{-2} \times K_{eq} \quad (8)$$

where, K_{eq} (M^{-1}) is the association constant which can be determined from the measurement of relative rate of aggregation in the presence of varying amounts of soluble hapten sugar¹⁷.

This kinetic method has advantages over that involving separation of the precipitin complex because it is simple and less time consuming²⁰. It also offers to estimate the contribution of factors that are often indicated to account for the increased agglutinability of transformed cells, *viz.* (i) receptor density, (ii) membrane fluidity (determined by the composition of lipid matrix), (iii) steric accessibility (*i.e.* influence of one on the other when two different types of glycoconjugates are present) and (iv) effect of head group. It is evident that the understanding of the molecular basis of these factors is, however, necessary in order to examine more critically the involvement of the cytoskeletal element. It may be emphasised here that few quantitative study has so far been made to establish the rate law of such complex process²¹. Nevertheless, the effect of receptor density, chemical nature of head group of phospholipid, carbohydrate sequence, cholesterol content on the agglutinability of vesicles bearing glycoconjugate have been examined either in terms of initial rate of change in turbidity or normalised first order rate constant when lectin is present in excess in various lectin liposomal systems.

The most important observation reported from the studies of vesicles containing GM₁ was that in the range of receptor concentration 2-10 mol% agglutination by lectin RCA₁ was extremely sensitive to receptor density (*i.e.* concentration in the plane of membrane). Thus, the rate of vesicle agglutination increased 20-fold when the mole ratio of GM₁ was from 1 : 123 to 1 : 55. A 4-fold increase in the rate is, however, expected for bimolecular aggregation. The apparent rate of vesicle agglutination was found to be sensitive to the cholesterol content of the vesicle¹⁸. In contrast, the apparent specificity of binding remains unchanged²². Apart from the concept of receptor density

TABLE 4—LIPOSOME BEARING GLYCOCONJUGATE AS MODEL FOR LECTIN-RECEPTOR INTERACTION AT CELL SURFACE

Lectin	Receptor	K_f $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	K_a M^{-1}
	1. Glycolipids		
RCA ₁	GM ₁ ^a	—	2.2×10^6
	Lactosyl ceramide ^b	1.4×10^6	8.7×10^6
	Gal-s. space gr o-cholesterol ^c	—	—
WGA	GM ₁ and GM ₂ ^d	—	—
	GM ₂ ^b	5.8×10^6	1.9×10^6
ConA	glc-fatty acid ^e	—	—
	2. Glycoproteins		
ConA	Band-3 ^f	—	$10^6 - 10^8$
Succinyl conA	Band-3 ^g	—	2.1×10^6
WGA	glycophorin ^h	—	2.5×10^6

^a Surolija *et al.*, *Nature (London)*, 1975, 257, 802. ^b S. K. Podder, Annual Report of CSIR project on 'Receptor-ligand interaction and transmembrane signalling', 1984. ^c Slama *et al.*, *Biochem.*, 1980, 19, 4595. ^d Redwood *et al.*, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1976, 455, 631. ^e Hampton *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 255, 6766. ^f Ketis *et al.*, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1982, 689, 194. ^g Chicken *et al.*, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1983, 729, 200. ^h Ketis *et al.*, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1983, 685, 347.

several other important concepts emerged from such studies listed in the Table 4. Rando and Bongter²³ established the concept of threshold concentration from the observation that the agglutination takes off dramatically at some 5 mol% receptor density. In addition, they were able to show that the agglutinability of a poor hapten can be improved by increasing length of spacer arm within certain limit²⁴. The latter is, however, reminiscent of the striking difference in agglutinability of vesicle bearing galactose ceramide and lactosyl ceramide²⁵. Others have shown that the accessibility of sugar group is controlled by the effective size of polar head group of phospholipid and introduced the concept of steric accessibility from the observation that the replacement of phosphatidyl choline by phosphatidyl ethanolamine confers agglutinability of glycolipid with a four-spacer arm embedded in zwitterionic PL (phosphatidyl choline) vesicles. In contrast, the agglutinability of PL vesicle containing glyco lipid ten-spacer arm remains unaffected^{26,27}.

Various studies on model membrane system indicated that vesicle size and its storage stability and transmembrane asymmetry is governed not only by the method of preparation but by its phospholipid composition and cholesterol content. Thus, it is rather difficult to make comment on the molecular mechanism leading to the observed variation of agglutinability of vesicles. Evidently transmembrane asymmetry (*i.e.* in plane distribution of embedded receptor) and surface potential and finally metastability of mixed vesicle system leading to alteration of vesicle size will most likely be important parameter to control the agglutinability of model membrane system (*i.e.* rate and extent of the precipitin reaction) in addition to the specificity, length of sugar sequence, anomericity of the α -carbon atom²⁸. The magnitude of specificity is determined not only by the chain length of sugar sequence and number of sugar residues that are accommodated in the cleft of binding site and finally, whether or not more than one site of lectin in the plane of membrane are involved in binding step as shown in the Fig. 3.

During the past several years efforts have been made in this laboratory to assess the individual contribution of the above mentioned various factors influencing the reactivity of glycoconjugates embedded in liposome and their correlation with the variations of agglutinability of liposome bearing glycoconjugates and of transformed cells.

We have, however, restricted ourselves to the study of glycoconjugate specially glycosphingolipid in the lipid vesicles with respect to their size, stability, transmembrane distribution and surface potential using various chemical probes, namely, monovalent neuraminidase, acridine orange and galactose specific lectins²⁹. The major emphasis has been to examine their possible receptor function towards lectin and toxin. Some of the interesting informations obtained are summarised here.

The transbilayer distribution of GD_{1a} in sonicated GD_{1a}-DPPC vesicles becomes increasingly asymmetric in favour of outer layer with increasing mole fraction of ganglioside (X_G) upto 0.5 and then levels off with 100% GD_{1a} in the outer surface. The surface charge density as monitored by metachromatic spectral shift of acridine orange in the presence of liposome bearing various mole percent of GD_{1a} also shows the same behaviour. The rate of desialation of GD_{1a} in the outer surface of lecithin matrix by neuraminidase when corrected for transbilayer distribution shows changes resembling composition dependent phase behaviour. This suggests that neuraminidase can be used as a probe for the study of the phase behaviour of lecithin-ganglioside system. The affinity and catalytic rate for desialation are inversely related suggesting the formation of non-productive enzyme-substrate complex ES at low X_G values presumably because of non-specific interaction between neuraminidase and liposome. In contrast, liposome bearing mixed ganglioside are unstable as reflected in the rate and amplitude of the precipitin reaction with WGA. They can be stabilised either by adding Ca²⁺ or incorporating lactosyl ceramide which then become cryptic towards RCA₁. Thus, surface potential seems to play an important role in controlling the reactivity and stability of liposome bearing gangliosides.

In view of this interesting finding, liposome bearing asialo-GM₁ is now being investigated to study specificity of well characterised galactose specific plant lectins, namely, peanut agglutinin (PNA), RCA₁ and plant toxin ricin. Fig. 4 shows the initial rate and amplitude of the precipitin reaction between vesicle containing asialo-GM₁ (2.9 μ M) by PNA, RCA₁, and ricin (RCA₂) at the same concentration of 2.26 μ M. It is seen that the initial rate of the reaction with PNA is lower than that of ricin and agglutinin, however, the final amplitude is found to be much higher in the case of PNA. Ricin reacts faster with a higher amplitude than agglutinin. This shows that the overall rate and mechanism of the precipitin reaction of vesicles by lectins is not solely determined by the valency of lectin. Other factors still to be identified are important as well.

Fig. 5 shows the corresponding dissociation curve of the precipitin complex in the presence of lactose. In the case of ricin and agglutinin, there is a very fast phase which can not be resolved. However, in the case of peanut lectin the very fast phase seems to be absent. The dissociation of both agglutinin- and ricin-asialo GM₁ system occur in μ M range of lactose concentration while that of PNA in the mM range.

Tables 5-7 summarise some of the preliminary data collected in this laboratory (*i.e.* the initial rate and amplitude of precipitin reaction of vesicles containing asialo-GM₁ with lectins, the $t_{1/2}$ values and their dependence of the concentration of sugar). The K_s (M^{-1}) and k_d values determined

Fig 4 Kinetics of precipitin reaction of vesicles containing asialo GM₁ (5% mole ratio of asialo GM₁ to DML, dimyristoyl lecithin) by PNA, RCA₁ and RCA₂ (concn of asialo GM₁ in vesicles = $2.9 \times 10^{-6} M$) (Δ) RCA₂, (●) PNA and (○) RCA₁, all $2.26 \times 10^{-6} M$

Fig 5 Kinetics of sugar (lactose) induced dissociation of the precipitin complex formed between vesicles containing asialo GM₁ and lectins (lactose concn. in parenthesis). (□) PNA-asialo GM₁ (28.8 mM), (○) RCA₁-asialo GM₁ (27.8 μM) and (●) RCA₂-asialo GM₁ (54.64 μM), protein = $2.26 \times 10^{-6} M$ asialo GM₁ = $2.9 \times 10^{-6} M$

TABLE 5—INITIAL RATE AND AMPLITUDE OF PRECIPITIN REACTION BETWEEN LECTIN AND LIPOSOME BEARING ASIALO GM₁

Lectin concn μM	Concn. of asialo GM ₁ μM	Initial rate (A ₃₄₀) × 10 ⁻³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Amplitude (A ₃₄₀ at 12 min)
PNA (2.26)	2.9	1.77	0.176
RCA ₁ (2.26)	2.9	1.28	0.105
RCA ₂ (2.26)	2.9	3.2	0.086

TABLE 6—DEPENDENCE OF t_{1/2} OF DISSOCIATION OF PRECIPITIN COMPLEX FORMED BETWEEN LECTIN AND LIPOSOME BEARING ASIALO GM₁ ON THE CONCENTRATION OF LACTOSE

Concn. of lectin μM	Concn. of asialo GM ₁ μM	Lactose concn μM	t _{1/2} s
PNA (2.26)	2.9	(a) 28.8*	480
		(b) 38"	288
		(c) 47.6"	240
RCA ₁ (2.26)	2.9	(a) 17.7	175
		(b) 27.8	144
		(c) 45.45	104
RCA ₂ (2.26)	2.9	(a) 20	300
		(b) 40	180
		(c) 54.64	120

* mM.

from concentration dependence of t_{1/2} on lactose as described here is also included in Table 7.

Conclusion :

It is clear from the above discussion that binding of lectin to liposome bearing simple glycosphingolipid is rather a complex process. The accessibility of exposed carbohydrate is controlled by a variety of factors, namely, surface charge, nature of polar head group of the lipid matrix and can be quantitatively expressed in terms of rate and extent of precipitin reaction. The specificity of

TABLE 7—BINDING PARAMETERS OF VARIOUS LECTINS TO ASIALO-GM₁

Lectin concn. μM	Asialo GM ₁ in vesicle μM	k_d^* s^{-1}	K_a^{**} M^{-1}
Ricin (RCA ₂) (2.26)	2.9	0.89	5.06×10^5 (4.65×10^5)
Agglutinin (RCA ₁) (2.26)	2.9	0.07	2.9×10^6
PNA (2.26)	2.9	4.5×10^{-4}	1.5×10^7

* Average value calculated from $t_{1/2}$ values given in Table 5 using the relation,

$$k_d = \frac{0.69}{t_{1/2} \times C_s \times K_{eq(s)}}$$

where, C_s is the concentration of sugar hapten and $K_{eq(s)}$ is the equilibrium constant for hapten to lectin.

** $K_a(M^{-1})$ was calculated using the relation,

$$K_a(\text{complex}) = \frac{k_{\sigma}(\text{simple})}{k_d(\text{complex})} \times K_{eq}(\text{simple})$$

The value in paranthesis is obtained independantly from the inhibition experiment of ricin.

binding of accessible carbohydrate to lectin is, however, comparable to those found for cell-lectin interaction. The results from these studies would also indicate existence of higher order complexity in the binding of lectin with model membrane bearing intrinsic membrane bound glycoproteins because not only the presence of multiple carbohydrate chain but also of their complex sugar sequence. Further complexity could arise from the variation of lipid-protein interaction which in turn may determine accessibility and orientation of carbohydrate. Grant and Sharon made pioneering studies on liposome bearing Band-3 protein (conA receptor) and glycophorin (WGA receptor) of human erythrocytes²⁰⁻²¹. The Band-3 protein is a folded polypeptide chain of approximately 96 000 D molecular weight with a single large N-linked carbohydrate chain. In contrast, glycophorin has a small polypeptide backbond (molecular weight of 12 000 D) which transverse only once and bears 16 short carbohydrate chains of which 15 are O-linked²²⁻²⁴. In both cases, binding of conA and WGA to the reconstituted glycoprotein was only observable in the presence of 3 mg ml⁻¹ albumin. The binding exhibits characteristics of co-operativity. This has been imposed a greater difficulty in the quantitation of binding. Recently it has been shown that conA reacts with surface of phospholipid-liposomes through two distinct classes of binding sites, a relatively small number of high affinity sites and a much larger number of low affinity sites. Addition of bovine serum albumin induces extensively additional binding of conA to liposomal membrane and this binding is saturable and specific, *i.e.* methyl mannoside inhibitable. In contrast, divalent succinyl conA shows little tendency to binding to liposome either in the presence or absence of albumin²⁵.

Either dramatic the conformation changes in conA due to succinylation or the repulsive barrier is too large for the nucleation of binding or a com-

ination of both could lead to such observation. For ligand induced vesicle agglutination as discussed here as well as cellular adhesion to occur there exists the repulsive barrier which need to be overcome. This can, however, be achieved in many different ways, namely, by increasing of number of non-covalent interaction, *viz.* hydrogen bonding by way of increasing receptor density, valency of the ligand and decreasing in surface charge density of the same sign. Among these the effect of receptor density and its distribution in the plane of membrane which is likely to be very sensitive to the host matrix composition has also been documented in other studies on model membrane bearing glycolipid hapten, *viz.* antibody binding and complement fixation and *in vivo* and *in vitro* cell-liposome interaction. The latter has, however, been investigated with regard to the development of organ specific delivery system²⁶. Finally, it may be emphasised once again that kinetics of the precipitin reaction between lectin and liposome bearing glycolipid and its dissociation in the presence of hapten sugar is extremely complex, however, gave interesting information. That it exhibits many features of complex agglutination reaction, *viz.* multiple type of binding, co-operativity even in the case of simple system, like GM₁-DPPC vesicles seem to suggest that involvement of factors, like membrane fluidity and cytoskeletal elements in giving rise to increased agglutinability of transformed cells has so far been over-emphasised. The exact molecular mechanism leading to such complex pattern in model system is not yet fully understood. It could partly be due to heterogeneity of vesicle sizes in the case of the GM₁-liposome-RCA₁ system. The observed co-operativity could also be due to unique conformation changes in lectin that might have been resulted from the binding of complex carbohydrate sequence at the liposome surface. It is known that binding simple sugar to lectin occurs in one step and is of non-cooperative

in nature. In contrast, the binding of lectin to carbohydrate sequence at the liposomal surface is co-operative in nature in some cases. If this be the case, the binding characteristics of simple saccharides does not seem to have much relevance in understanding lectin mediated phenomena. It is evident that further insight into the molecular mechanism of lectin mediated phenomena is likely to be obtained from the further indepth studies of precipitin reaction hitherto described. Work in this direction is in progress in the laboratory.

Acknowledgement

This work is financially supported by C.S.I.R. and D.S.T., New Delhi.

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